

Storytelling : tool of attraction and mobilization of the moroccan qualified diaspora

Le storytelling : outil d'attraction et de mobilisation de la diaspora marocaine qualifiée

Yassine MATOUG

PhD student

National School of Business and Management of Kenitra

Ibn Tofail University

The Organizational Management Sciences Research Laboratory

Morocco

Ilham BOURIQUI

PhD, Full Professor

National School of Business and Management of Kenitra

Ibn Tofail University

The Organizational Management Sciences Research Laboratory

Morocco

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Abstract :

In a context of globalization that has characterized the international mobility flows of highly qualified migrants. The issue of attracting and mobilizing skilled workers has become a priority for countries around the world and more specifically for developing countries. Indeed, territories and organizations are in competition to attract the best talents. Morocco aware of this challenge at the crossroads of civilizations, known for its rich history of emigration continues to undergo different forms of human mobility. The theory of economic catch-up of migration emphasizes the importance of brain gain at the expense of a brain drain. The Moroccan diaspora represent a reservoir of talents that could be put at the service of the development of the morrocan economy. Indeed the practice of storytelling as a marketing tool and branding drawing its origins from the field of narratology could constitute an interesting track to influence the perceptions of the moroccan diaspora highly qualified to generate the expected behaviour. Our research objective is to contribute to scientific and managerial reflections on the potential of adopting a branding approach by conceptualizing storytelling in the process of attraction and mobilization of the qualified diaspora for the development of the moroccan economy. Indeed, the practice of storytelling has been used in different contexts such as the consumption of goods, tourism and recruitment to generate a good reputation and increase the trust ratio within the targeted community.

Keys words:

Storytelling; Communication/Marketing; Qualified diaspora; Attraction; Representation.

Résumé :

Dans un contexte de mondialisation ayant marqué les flux de mobilité internationale des migrants hautement qualifiés. La question d'attraction et de mobilisation des compétences des diasporas est devenue une priorité pour les pays du globe et plus spécifiquement les pays en voie de développement. En effet, les territoires et les organisations sont entrés dans une compétition pour attirer les meilleurs talents. Le Maroc conscient de ce challenge au carrefour des civilisations, connu par sa riche histoire d'émigration continue de subir différentes formes de mouvements humains. La théorie du rattrapage économique de la migration souligne l'importance du brain gain au détriment d'un brain drain. La diaspora marocaine constituant un réservoir de compétences pourrait être mise au service du développement économique du Maroc. En effet la pratique de storytelling comme outil marketing et du branding tirant ses origines du domaine de la narratologie pourrait constituer une piste intéressante pour influencer les perceptions de la diaspora marocaine hautement qualifiée pour engendrer le comportement attendu. Notre objectif de recherche est de contribuer aux réflexions scientifiques et managériales sur le potentiel d'adopter une approche branding en conceptualisant le storytelling dans le processus d'attraction et mobilisation de diaspora qualifiée pour le développement de l'économie marocaine. En effet, cet outil a été utilisé dans différents contextes comme celui de la consommation des biens, le tourisme et le recrutement afin de générer une bonne réputation et augmenter le ratio de confiance au sein de la communauté ciblée.

Mots clés :

Storytelling; Communication/Marketing; Diaspora qualifiée; Attraction; Représentation.

Introduction

In a globalized world marked by a tough competition between territories and organizations to attract skilled workers in various fields such as medicine, technology etc, this new reality with the advent of the New Public Management paradigm has given importance to the concept of attractiveness representing a major stake in the achievement of economic development (Anttiroiko, 2015). This context has pushed organizations and territories to adopt the brand as a marketing tool to convey the image desired by decision makers to identify and differentiate themselves from the competition. The concept of storytelling as a tool of the brand represents a key concept in shaping the brand image of the territory/ organization with its targets.

Indeed, talents from the moroccan diaspora have a special attention of HIS MAJESTY the KING of Morocco who expressed it in several of his speeches, and has been translated in the 2011 Moroccan constitution, and the new development model of 2021, considering moroccans living abroad as a development agents. It's important to notice that the qualified diaspora represent more than 15% of the total of moroccans living abroad estimated at more than five million people be a skill pool of more than 800,000 skilled people.

The question of the attachment of these talents to their country of origin can be a great opportunity for moroccan territories and organizations wishing to attract and mobilize these target to benefit from the expertise and the rich experiences accumulated in the host countries. Indeed, several reports of international organizations have made the link between the migration relationship and development through the contribution of the diaspora which will allow the country of origin to gain skills, and benefit of the knowledge transfer and create a diplomatic effect by strengthening bilateral agreements in areas of mutual interest.

Branding allows developing positive perceptions of a brand in the mind of its target audience. It has become a necessity for territories and organizations wishing to differentiate themselves in a competitive environment. In this context, storytelling has gained space in the marketing field in general. Storytelling has been part of the human being since its existence (Gerber et al., 2013).

Thus, it is easy to understand why storytelling has become one of the tools increasingly used by organizations to enrich the brand image (Godin, 2011). The need for additional information from targets pushes organizations to reinforce this image and, to do so, storytelling has proven to be a very effective tool (Gilliam et al., 2013). It should be mentioned that the concept of storytelling has its origins in the field of narratology and has made its entrance in the

management sciences of organizations and specifically in the discipline of marketing and more precisely in the content marketing component.

Storytelling has proven to be a branding tool of choice. On the one hand, stories capture the target audience attention and will be easier to remember. This facilitates the sharing of information about the brand and its values. On the other hand, they are more able to awaken the emotions of the target and thus allow a real emotional connection between the two parties. (Tengti Kao, 2019). Brand storytelling is therefore a powerful marketing tool, making it possible to attract and engage individuals with a brand, while building or strengthening a long-term relationship of trust with consumers (du Plessis, 2015).

Recent research shows that the art of storytelling creates and maintains a competitive brand advantage, by shaping consumer attachment to it. Moreover, storytelling is gradually proving its effectiveness in changing perceptions (Tengti Kao, 2019). All these possibilities make storytelling a relevant branding tool.

Our scientific contribution is therefore interested in the question of attraction and mobilization of the qualified diaspora by adopting a branding approach based on storytelling relying on the theory of social representations and the theory of trust.

Our problematic focuses on how storytelling as a brand tool contribute to the attraction and mobilization of the highly qualified diaspora? Our research objective is to contribute to scientific and managerial reflections on the potential of adopting a brand approach by using storytelling in the attraction and mobilization of qualified diaspora for the development of moroccan economy.

This theoretical scientific paper adopts a methodology of an exploratory nature for several reasons, including the polysemic nature of the concept of territory and the multidisciplinary nature of the issue of attractiveness that intersects with geography, social psychology, and marketing as a discipline of management sciences and the dynamic nature of the brand. As part of this research, several official reports, official speeches, theses and scientific papers were consulted in order to conceptualize the issue of attracting and mobilizing moroccan qualified diaspora through a brand approach with a focus on storytelling.

This scientific paper gives at first a literature review presenting an overview on moroccan migration, and key concepts related to our research. The second section will be devoted to theoretical framework of this scientific paper. The third section will be dedicated to the presentation of our conceptual model. The conclusion will highlight academic and managerial implications and research limits and perspectives.

1. Literature Review

1.1 Overview on the moroccan migration

The migration of moroccan people is a trend that dates back to colonial times. After going through different stages, a diversification of locations and change in the demographic and socioeconomic characteristics of the diaspora has been witnessed. In 2021, about 6 million of moroccans are living abroad, the equivalent of 15% of the total Moroccan population. Men first migrated after World War II, when Europe needed labor force to rebuild, and the trend accelerated sharply in the strong economic growth in 1960s. The 1970s saw a change in the nature of migration and a gradual transformation in the characteristics of migrants. The migration of men was followed by family reunification. The feminization of the Moroccan diaspora has continued since 1980.

France, Spain, Italy, Belgium, Canada and the United States are the most important destinations for moroccans. Since at least the 1990s, the Moroccan government has made major efforts to reach out the morrocans living abroad through a specialized ministry. The 2011 Moroccan Constitution includes provisions intended to facilitate the mobilization of the moroccan diaspora and encourage them to contribute to Morocco's development.

His MAJESTY, Mohammed the Sixth, The King of Morocco pays a special attention to moroccans living abroad. Indeed, in several of his speeches the Sovereign launched an appeal to the governmental actors to enhance the quality of administrative services dedicated to this population strongly attached to its country of origin, and set up a mechanism that encourages the mobilization of investors and skilled people from the Moroccan diaspora to foster the development of their country of origin in the strategic sectors launched by the morrocan state in the later years.

The success of any programme of mobilization and attraction of these talents from the diaspora is conditioned by several factors of attractiveness of the territory and organizations, and the involvement of all stakeholders and the meeting of several conditions in order to meet the challenges of economic development. The attraction and mobilization of highly qualified Moroccans living abroad is linked in a certain manner to the image of the country, its economic brand, and the representation of the attractiveness of moroccan territories and organizations.

Storytelling as a brand tool was chosen due to the lack of scientific literature that is interested in the diaspora, attractiveness, and brand image, which in our opinion have close connections. Several official documents and reports have highlighted that the diaspora represents a network of ambassadors awaiting activation (dunning, 2008).

The diaspora has been identified by some experts as a soft power of the country of origin, serving as a complementary actor in governmental public diplomacy and in promoting the image of the country of origin in various sectors of activities. Its successful integration into the host society is reflected in achievements at the political level, economic, scientific, etc., which facilitate constructive and pragmatic dialogue with indigenous people occupying strategic positions, thus offering opportunities for foreign direct investment and collaborations in terms of transfer of knowledge.

It should be recalled that the constitution of Morocco of 2011 guarantees all the rights to the moroccan community established abroad and that the year 2015 saw the official launch of the National Strategy in favour of Moroccans of the World under the Enlightened Vision of HM the King of Morocco and which has three major pillars: the preservation of the moroccan identity; the protection of the rights and interests of moroccans living abroad; Making the moroccans living abroad contribute to the development of the country.

Mobilizing the skills and investments of the diaspora is a significant challenge for any country seeking development. It should be recalled that Morocco's 2021 New Development Model has placed great importance on mobilizing the moroccan diaspora to achieve the expected development goals.

1.1.1 From BRAIN DRAIN to BRAIN GAIN

Initially, the historical-structural theory pointed out the negative effect that unskilled labor migration had on the countries of origin, which corresponded to economic reality until the Second World War. Since then, new migratory trends are emerging. Now this phenomenon affects not only the unskilled but also the highly qualified migrants.

In the early 1970s, with the mass emigration of engineers and medical staff between Europe, Canada, and the United States, a new debate arose, particularly about the impact of skilled labor mobility. Debates on this type of migration come together under the concept of «brain drain». The concept was born in a publication of the British Royal Society in 1963.

The term brain drain is emerging as a synonym for a large number of scientists leaving Britain to go to the United States. Later the concept finds application in the case of flows of skilled workers from developing countries. These discussions raised alarm bells about the negative effects of the departure of qualified people on the development process in the countries of origin. In the early 1990s, there is a new wave of research that is providing a more optimistic

view of the effects of skilled migration on the destination countries, highlighting the potential for 'brain drain with brain gain' (Stark, et al 1997).

The positive role played by migration in the increase of human capital in countries of origin is defined as the result of “incentive effects” In addition, other positive effects such as: remittances return migration or networks have been highlighted being named as “return effects” (ex-post, feedback effects) (Lodigiani, 2009).

1.1.2 Mobilization of the Moroccan qualified diaspora

The mobilization program of the qualified diaspora launched by the ministerial department in charge of moroccans living abroad consists in calling on members of this diaspora with expertise, experience and know-how who are ready to contribute to the development of Morocco in a timely or sustainable way. The interest in this program is justified by tree main reasons: Existence of highly qualified profiles among the Moroccan diaspora who expressed a strong will to contribute to the development of their country of origin; Existence of ambitious sectoral plans in Morocco; The political will of public authorities to promote this type of contribution.

On the basis of these elements, the Ministerial Department of Moroccans living abroad based the objectives of its program, namely: To provide a framework for these targeted skilled workers to inform them about the opportunities of their contribution; To enable them to develop partnerships with Moroccan public and private actors; and including these partnerships in the framework of bilateral and multilateral cooperation.

This approach was implemented through the creation of geographical networks (Germany, Canada, United States, Switzerland, France) and thematic such as (Network of Medical Skills of the worlds Morrocan, network of Moroccan business leaders of the World, network of Moroccan journalists of the World, network of Moroccan Lawyers of the World, Network of Moroccan skilled workers in aeronautics in Canada).

In Morocco, public policies targeting highly qualified diaspora are designed in terms of skills mobilization policies. In 2012, the The Council of the Moroccan Community Abroad (CCME) published a study that reviews institutional and associative experiences since the 1990s related to this context. In this work, a broad definition was highlighted to designate the notion of «skilled». This should concern any person living abroad, temporarily or permanently, with professional, scientific, technical, artistic, cultural or associative expertise, who could satisfy a well-identified need in the public or private sector; or meet the human resource needs of sectoral

development plans and programmes; or participate in any project at the territorial or national level, requiring human resource strengthening in Morocco (El Asri, 2012). This definition was built through operational means, taking into consideration the Moroccan proposal to encourage the active participation of its highly qualified diaspora in sectors in high demand for resources. After the experimentation of several programs of mobilization of the Moroccan diaspora like the Transfer of Knowledge Through Expatriate Nationals (TOKTEN) of the UNITED NATIONS DEVELOPEMENT PROGRAM (UNDP) and the FINCOME program of the National Center of Scientific and Technical Research (CNRST) some shortcomings hindered the achievement of the expected objectives.

Considering this mixed assessment of these programs, The Royal Speech on the occasion of the 69th anniversary of the revolution of the King and the People was an opportunity for the Sovereign to recall his esteem and express his sense of pride towards the Moroccan community established abroad who plays an important role in defending the national interests at their head the question of the territorial integrity, standing out in several fields (politics, economy, science, culture, sports) and strongly attached to the values of their motherland. This Royal Speech was also an opportunity to point out the inadequacy of the governance established in the management of this file and urge the Government to review the institutional and governance framework and design a mechanism that will best meet the expectations of talents and project leaders in terms of identification and support. Indeed, these Royal Directives announced a new dynamic at the level of the Department of Moroccans Living Abroad which multiplied meetings and consultations with stakeholders involved in the management of this file. These meetings have led to the creation of 5 commissions working on: Upgrading and reforming the institutional framework for Moroccans living abroad; Encouraging Moroccans living abroad investments in Morocco; Mobilizing expertise; Administrative services for Moroccans of the World; Cultural, educational and religious supervision.

1.2 The concept of Trust

Trust is a term that has been extensively studied by researchers in a variety of disciplines, including sociologists, psychologists, economists, and political scientists. There is a wide range of definitions of trust and it can mean different things in different situations. Cultural and institutional factors also play a significant role in the perception and experience of trust. Trust is often viewed as a fundamental factor in social and economic relationships. It facilitates cooperation and coordination between people and groups. Trust can also be considered as a

social capital. It helps to build social networks and contributes to the overall prosperity of a society.

The concept of trust was first mobilized in psychology and sociology. The first meaning attributed to trust (Giffin, 1967; Rotter, 1971) is a belief that a partner is trustworthy and high-trustworthy. In sociology, trust was seen as a fundamental assumption of humanity about the permanence and effectiveness of social structures, both moral and natural. Without trust, society would become chaotic and uncertain, as individuals would not be able to rely on each other or work together efficiently. Trust is seen as a fundamental component of social order. When it comes to economic analysis, the concept of trust is presented as a rational calculation to minimize transaction costs by assessing the gains from the exchange (Williamson, 1993). In the psychoanalytic approach, however, trust is seen as an upstream of intention because it is presented as a predictor of future behaviour.

The relational approach emphasizes the need to build long-lasting relationships with consumers and other interested parties in order to generate value. (Morgan, 1994) and (Ganesan, 1994) were of the most influential contributors to this approach, emphasizing the importance of trust and engagement in building and sustaining long-lasting relationships. "Trust," Ganesan wrote, "is the essential element of relationships. It is the faith in the other party's competence, trustworthiness, and good intentions." By establishing trust with consumers, companies can establish a basis for long-lasting relationships and build customer loyalty. In the public sector, trust in public organizations is a key component to achieve the expected results.

By this definition, it implicitly responds to (Moorman et al., 1993), who argue that intention is an implicit element of the definition. To them, the action of the intention intervenes because "the intention is understood as a consequence of the attitude rather than as a part of its definition". Therefore, "the intention to trust" should be understood as the result of the trust rather than as part of the definition". "intentional trust", as defined by Luhmann, (1979), (Giddens, 1990) or (Zaheer et al., 1998), characterizes the trust that individuals place in other individuals. It is seen as an essential social resource that promotes cooperation and enables better coordination of interactions.

Inter organisational trust is defined as "the trust that the members of the organization have in the associated organization" (Zaheer et al, 1998). Inter organisational trust extends beyond the person-to-person relationship to the partner organization that the exchange takes place with. For (Doney & Cannon, 1997), interpersonal trust may be at the root of organizational trust and vice versa. Neo-institutional economics emphasizes the need for organizations to balance the

demands of efficiency with the need to ensure that the interests of various stakeholders are aligned. Organizations use a mix of market-oriented mechanisms (e.g. contracts, outsourcing, etc.) and hierarchical arrangements (e.g., internalization) to coordinate their economic activity. Market-oriented mechanisms are often viewed as a more effective way of coordinating economic activity. However, they can also lead to problems of “opportunity” and “information asymmetry”, where one party has an incentive to exploit the other.

1.3 New Public Management

The emergence of the New Public Management is the result of a gap between a private sector better equipped than a public sector facing several challenges in terms of management in all dimensions. The goal of this New Public Management is to establish within the administration a new constructive approach inspired by the performance of the private sector to make it a citizen and democratic administration. Indeed, this citizen administration must be part of a mind-set inspired by Customer Relationship Management that advocates efficiency in taking into accounts the expectations and aspirations of citizens within the framework of an effective and transparent communication approach. This new context has encouraged public sector organizations to draw practices from the private sector toolbox to make it more efficient and efficient.

1.4 Branding

Branding has become a key skill for organizations, this term refers to the strategic practice of creating and managing brands and their image as valuable assets of the organization (Swystun, 2006). A branding approach aims to develop positive perceptions of a brand in the mind of its target audience. The essence of the approach lies in the need to differentiate and offer the consumer a value perceived as unique (Keller, 2019). To do this, the brand manager will play on the projected image of the brand, to try to change the image actually perceived by the consumer (Bastos & Levy, 2012).

There are many dimensions of a brand image of an organization: the desired image, the perceived image, the projected image, and finally the possible image (Libaert & Johannes 2016). The desired image represents the organization’s vision for its brand, the values and intentions it wishes to give it and the way it would like to be perceived by its target audience. The perceived image is then how the brand is actually perceived by this target. The possible image requires an analysis of the surrounding context. Depending on this environment, what are the really attainable perceptions for this brand? Finally, the projected image includes all the

messages issued by the organization about its brand, the way it presents it concretely (Libaert & Johannes 2016).

Branding aims to match the desired image and the perceived image. For this purpose, it can play on the projected image, taking into account what it is possible or not to achieve at a given time and context (Bastos & Levy, 2012). Branding helps to build and defend the reputation of a brand, understood as the sum of images perceived over time (Libaert & Johannes, 2016).

1.5 Storytelling

Storytelling is the oldest but also the most modern art used by human beings for different actions, including to transmit information, circulate ideas, give meaning to the environment in which we live, give a cultural, moral and territorial dimension, to which we will refer throughout our life (Godin 2011; Gilliam, et al., 2013). Storytelling is also a very powerful way to strengthen and create emotional connections with those around us but also with any image or brand (Herskovitz & Malcolm, 2010).

Through stories, our parents and grandparents help us to understand the environment and the events that characterize it, in a way that enables us to identify and distinguish between good and evil. According to Lewi (2014) the definition of storytelling is much deeper than telling a story to any external listener, it is a true combination of techniques designed in such a way as to first captivate the attention of the target audiences and then convince them. In this specific way of telling stories, the internal message is elaborated in a precise way, following very specific rules and methods that are specific to the narration (Gerber et al., 2013).

To be able to talk about storytelling, the story must be inserted into a specific context and the basic ideas of the creation must allow the narrator to concretely convince the recipient and make him adhere to a clear, true and definitive conclusion (Gerber et al., 2013). This process is very important especially in the field of marketing, where consumers' belief in the validity of the product is necessary to ensure the success of the brand and to get the public to adhere to the cause supported by the brand (Lewi, 2014). Storytelling is therefore an art in itself because it requires a great know-how on the part of the narrator, in terms of creativity and style, to be able to effectively convince the listener of his point of view and ultimately create a bond of trust between narrator and recipient.

True and powerful story is important in all areas where storytelling is used, but its real vocation is “to defend a cause, to direct story towards a political, commercial, personal goal and to drive adherence. Its purpose is to change one’s mind, to make one think, to change the

attitude and behaviour of the person to whom it is addressed” (Lewi, 2014). According to the same author, different types of stories exist, but not all of them are storytelling. However, any type of language can be a source of storytelling. A story can be presented in written, oral, or visual form and even a simple solicitation of one of the five senses we have can make us recall a story, a time that is dense with meaning for us and that can lead us to a different interpretation of the environment.

The main purpose of storytelling is to arouse a desire for action, participation, change or movement in order to push the listener towards a new ideology that will then be adopted (Lewi, 2014) cited by (Hennaut, 2020).

The techniques used to produce storytelling are consistent with complete narrative structures that aim to entertain, distract the audience but also to persuade and adhere to conclusions that are dictated by the narrator (Gerber et al., 2013).

According to Gerber et al. (2013), storytelling can be summarized by three fundamental actions, the three C’s that define storytelling:

- Capture attention: for example, by using an approach in the form of a question exposing the problem, the plot tries to draw the listener to a new world created by the narrator;
- Captivate: by continuing the story with its initial situation, its characters, its twists, etc.; the listener is transported into a story that will make him attentive to its development;
- Convince: by delivering a “moral” or more rational elements.

These three Cs are the basis of the process of creating storytelling in any field.

The persuasion and conviction of the interlocutor are the basis of the storytelling creation process (Lewi, 2014).

Stories are told for different reasons. They help anyone to organize past experiences; they create order and provide an explanation for unusual events and a perspective that allows an assessment of future events.

According to (Schank, 1995), there are three types of reasons why a person tells stories:

1. Satisfaction with simply telling a story;
2. Satisfaction with the observable effects that story has on listeners after listening to our story;
3. Effect of this story in the conversation you are participating in.

According to (Schank, 1995), telling a story is an integral part of our need to have people around

us with whom we can share these sensations and memories. The ultimate goal is to coordinate past events with present events. This understanding of past events allows people to build their behaviours accordingly in order to guide their future behaviours.

According to (Lundqvist et al., 2012), few empirical studies have been conducted on storytelling. Recently, organizations have begun to reconsider storytelling and its potential in order to distinguish themselves from the competition (Lundqvist et al., 2012). An increase in research in this area, as described by (Chang, 2009), has been observed as a result of a desire to better understand consumer attitudes towards the brand after experiences cited by (Lundqvist et al., 2012).

Several authors have analyzed different facets of this tool known but little considered so far in the field of marketing. (Stern's, 2004) studies provide an analysis of the impact of stories in advertising and corporate communication cited by (Ludqvist et al., 2012). (Escalas, 2004) offers various studies on the capacity of storytelling to persuade individuals and the use of stories as a connection between the brand and consumers.

1.5.1 Storytelling as a means of marketing communication

According to (Gilliam et al. 2013), storytelling is an important element of marketing communication. Story allows a wider range of information to be communicated, in an acceptable way because it is an effective tool for building and developing relationships with the public. Stories are also an element used by consumers to judge a new product, to understand and analyze new experiences and, in general, to make decisions that concern different areas (Adaval & Wyer, 1998). Indeed, each person uses his past experiences to judge the validity of a new product. Therefore, we can understand the importance of using storytelling as a means of communication, in order to make the product as acceptable as possible.

1.5.2 Storytelling as a means of integrated communication

According to (Armstrong et al. 2010), "integrated marketing communication takes into account all the contacts between the consumer and the company or its brands. Each contact delivers a positive, negative or neutral message. Of course, the company wants to deliver a consistent and positive message at every opportunity."

The story can be adapted and integrated for all the tools that make up the communication mix; in this way storytelling can become a very useful and important element to ensure consistency (Lundqvist et al., 2012).

More specifically, integrated marketing communication allows the creation of a global communication strategy that creates a relationship with the customer and, ultimately, the customer's belief in the validity of the products and the satisfaction of all their needs (Armstrong et al., 2010).

Thanks to these specific characteristics, especially the fact of attracting attention to convince afterwards, storytelling is a particularly suitable element for the creation and dissemination of messages of univocal brands (Lewi, 2014). To make storytelling effectively usable, different messages must be linked in a way that makes the company's marketing communication credible (Armstrong et al., 2010). This last element is essential for the success of storytelling and for the creation of a lasting relationship with consumers (Armstrong et al., 2010).

1.5.3 Storytelling in the marketing field

Marketing encompasses all these activities that affect the consumer and its main purpose is to create profitable and lasting relationships with the consumer (Armstrong et al., 2010). The main objectives of marketing are much broader than simply selling a product to customers (Armstrong et al., 2010). This includes the dissemination of ideas and the creation of a link with the client in order to satisfy all their needs (Armstrong et al., 2010; Godin, 2011). Indeed, according to (Godin, 2011), the diffusion of ideas is the basis of value creation and the main form of diffusion of knowledge and experiences.

To make these values vivid, they must be introduced into a story and dynamic contexts with powerful images (Fog et al., 2005). According to (Fog et al., 2005), stories have the power to frame values in a clearly defined perspective and human context in order to give them a precise meaning defined by the company. Unlike other means of disseminating information, story makes it possible to mix feelings with reason, an element that makes this instrument indispensable for better marketing communication (Gerber et al., 2013).

1.5.4 Brand Storytelling

Scientific research has shown that stories play a major role in our memorization process (Herskovitz & Malcolm, 2010). Where rational arguments, raw facts or statistics are quickly forgotten, a story will be more easily remembered. Intuitively, we are more sensitive to it and judge the stories more convincing than a list of arguments as complete as it is (Delgado-Ballester & Fernández-Sabiote, 2016). This is explained in particular by the emotional impact of a story, which stimulates our five senses by referring to our own past experiences (Hsiu-Ping & Yi-Lun, 2019).

Storytelling thus represents one of the oldest and most powerful modes of communication (Delgado-Ballester & Fernández-Sabiote, 2016). Storytelling has proven to be a branding tool of choice. On the one hand, stories capture the consumer's attention more and will be easier to remember. This facilitates the sharing of information about the brand and its values. On the other hand, they are more able to awaken the emotions of the consumer and thus allow a real emotional connection between the two parties. (Tengti Kao, 2019).

Brand storytelling is therefore a powerful marketing tool, making it possible to attract and engage individuals with a brand, while building or strengthening a long-term relationship of trust with consumers (du Plessis, 2015). Recent research shows that the art of storytelling creates and maintains a competitive brand advantage, by shaping consumer attachment to it. Moreover, storytelling is gradually proving its effectiveness in changing consumer perceptions (Tengti Kao, 2019). All these possibilities make storytelling a relevant branding tool, surfing on the evolution of consumers and their interest in useful, relevant, informative, playful or entertaining content (Herskovitz & Malcolm, 2010 ; Henrard & Pierra, 2015).

1.5.5 The 4 fundamentals of the story

When it comes to building a story, there is no universal method (Denning, 2006). However, every story is structured to captivate its audience. Each story has a starting point, a middle and an ending situation. Events unfold in a chronological sequence, commonly referred to as a plot. (Lundqvist, Liljander, Gummerus, & van Riel, 2012). (Fog, 2010), (Paquette, Yang, & Long (2017) & Lundqvist (2012) agree that a narrative is built around four elements: a message, a conflict, characters, and a plot, or action.

- ❖ **The message:** According to (Fog, 2010) storytelling is a means, not an end. It is important to define the goal. Successful storytelling conveys messages that convey a positive brand image. But it is important to think about what message to communicate. And it requires an upstream strategy. The success of the message depends mainly on the contingent objectives and the coherence between the objective and the narrative.
- ❖ **The conflict:** Conflict is the driving force behind a good story (Woodside, 2010). The reason is the human nature. Throughout our lives, we seek balance, harmony with our environment, with ourselves. Therefore, when our tranquillity is threatened, our instinct pushes us to act. We are able to put in place everything in our power to regain the initial harmony. Thus, stress or danger push us to act: the conflict is the engine of action (Fog, 2010).

- ❖ **The characters:** Another fundamental element of any brand story is the presence of characters. The distribution of their role and characteristics are essential elements for a successful story, which effectively conveys the message. To exist, conflict needs compelling characters interacting with each others. It's important to highlight the notion of archetype and stability: Archetypes: One of the most relevant reasoning for approaching brand image is based on collective consciousness. In this collective consciousness, we find «archetypes» as shared social constructions emanating from different sources like religions, literatures, films ect. In the case of brand storytelling, the use of archetypes manifests itself primarily in the types of a particular archetype. It amounts to building one's character around a model of a "universally familiar character" (Delgado-Ballester & Fernández-Sabiote, 2016). According to Tsai (2006), the use of archetypes in marketing finds its purpose in the search for identity that the individual pursues, through the consumption behavior. Thus, the consumer must be able to both recognize and identify with the archetype used (Tsai, 2006); Stability: Characters in a brand storytelling strategy can experience countless adventures. Nevertheless, consumers need some stability between the different narratives of the same brand. This in order to fully understand the subtleties of the characters in place, but also for the sake of general consistency.
- ❖ **The plot:** Once the message is defined, the conflict specified and the characters constructed, it is a matter of building the story itself. Every story has an starting point, a middle and a final situation, articulated in chronological order. This sequence of consecutive events is called the plot (Lundqvist, Liljander, Gummerus, & van Riel, 2012). The sequence of events must be sufficiently worked to maintain public interest throughout (Fog, 2010). From the outset, it is important that the first actions generate interest. (Lundqvist, Liljander, Gummerus, & van Riel, 2012). As soon as the initial situation is established, the theme and tone of the story are introduced. Then comes the conflict, a follow of an escalation of events putting the characters to the test and thus allowing them to illustrate themselves. In the case of a success story where the founder plays the role of the hero, the latter may experience various difficulties in launching his ingenious idea.

1.6 Place and narrative

The recognition of the role of language in the construction of social reality has led to an intellectual evolution in the social sciences (followed by management and research on consumers) under the sign of poststructuralism. Theorists question the traditional conception of language as a transparent and direct representation of objects in the world, and propose the idea that language does not reflect social reality, but it is involved in the social construction of reality (Alvesson & Kärreman 2000).

According to (Lichrou et al 2017), the semiotician Daniel Chandler points out that "all words are "abstractions", and there is no direct relationship between words and "things" in the world". According to this perspective, «reality and truth are constructed by the practices of representation and interpretation of rhetoric and its listeners» (Brown 1994) cited by (Lichrou et al., 2017).

According to Elliott (1996), language encompasses elements of social action and function. It is essential to become aware of and take into account the significant uses of language by individuals in describing social situations and experiences. According to the same author "individuals intentionally use language to create representations or versions of society, this construction process being illustrated by the variation of language». However, it should be noted that the poststructuralist approach to language may not be adapted in more pragmatic situations, such as the design and use of train timetables, where the importance of benefits and functions inevitably requires a perception of language as a "representation of reality". However, this does not apply in the context of the study of complex social phenomena "constituted from a specific vocabulary" (Alvesson & Kärreman, 2000). In this situation, it is beneficial to recognize the functions of language that go beyond the mere representation of an "externality". This is of great importance in the analysis of the place, as a "distinctive meeting in time" (Agnew, 2011).

Narrative is beneficial for the study of places because of its link with language and the way individuals co-create social reality. First, narration is the main form of knowledge and communication between human beings. Referring to the moral philosopher Alasdair MacIntyre, (Czarniawska, 2004) cited by (Lichrou, et al 2017) proposes the idea that social life can be considered as an ongoing story. The perception of reality is essentially mental (Hudson & Ozanne, 1988). By adopting a narrative ontology, we recognize that individuals construct social reality through narratives (Hopkinson & Hogarth-Scott, 2001).

According to (Bruner, 2004) cited by (Lichrou et al., 2017), individuals primarily perceive their experiences in the world as stories, which is why their experiences are also structured as stories. In this perspective, «narrative imitates life, life imitates narration». It is therefore conceivable to understand reality as a narrative created by the human imagination.

According to Guba and Lincoln cited by (Lichrou et al., 2017) , there is no real, unique and objective reality, but rather "several, intangible mental constructions, based on society and experience, local and specific in their nature and which depend for their form and content on the individuals or groups that maintain them". We perceive the world individually, but our perceptions are rooted in social interactions. Daily life involves constant interaction and communication with others (Berger & Luckman, 1967). It is for this reason that social reality is characterized by intersubjectivity and negotiation of meanings between individuals (Berger and Luckman 1967). Therefore, our world narratives depend on the socio-cultural contexts in which we find ourselves, because this context is the medium of our view of the world. In other words, "social narratives limit the possibilities of personal narrative" (Hopkinson & Hogarth-Scott, 2001).

Indeed, even if we as individuals perceive reality through our subjective narratives of our experiences in the world, our narratives are not autonomous, but "always written in specific cultural terms" (Thompson et al., 1994). In creating our own narratives, we are constrained by the norms of our culture and socially determined discourses, which spread across society (Shankar et al. 2001). Therefore, narratives are not only structures of meaning, but also structures of power (Turner & Bruner, 1986), they highlight certain realities and silence others according to dominant interests.

However, as (Shankar et al., 2001) point out, this is not done unilaterally: «discourse also establishes social structures in a dialectical relationship, and individual symbolic actions play a social role by collectively restructuring the orders of discourse». This also contributes to an understanding of the place as a mixture of intersubjective stories.

Narratives, whether fictional or real, are forms of association (Czarniawska, 2004). Therefore, what matters from a narrative perspective is the relationship between events and experiences, as well as the process by which meanings are generated, rather than the veracity of events (Czarniawska, 2004). It is therefore emphasized that the narrative approach emphasizes the possibility of acquiring knowledge by studying how individuals construct their reality - and in the case of place branding, how individuals construct places. Storytelling plays a crucial role in

the interaction between individuals and places, contributing to their social construction (Lichrou, et al, 2014).

Place meanings are constructed through direct and indirect experience of places (Gunderson & Watson, 2007), and interactions with others (Kyle & Chick, 2007), and through the plethora of narratives (generated by marketers, tourists and locals) that circulate about the place. Marketer-generated narratives (in advertising, brochures etc.) offer powerful spatialising discourses that help to create ‘imaginary geographies’ (Hopkins, 1998), and to make indistinct the limits between reality and perception (Larsen & George, 2006). Place brands are social constructions aimed at strengthening the local identity and offering a unique offer to potential investors and tourists. A place brand like this can be established in a process from the top down by destination marketing organizations. However, this method has been criticized because there is often a disparity between the desired image and the lived reality (Columb & Kalandides, 2010). According to (Lichrou, et al., 2017) place narratives can be beneficial for developing a thoughtful and collaborative branding process, as they offer marketers opportunities to explore the diverse, interactive and dynamic realities of the place. Indeed, narratives offer different perspectives to understand the place. Access to experiences through storytelling does not automatically create a unified view of what a place is or should be. Indeed, the process of organizing and interpreting multiple narratives must be undertaken in a reflexive way and this must also be reflected in the final process of creating the brand of the place. This involves being aware of the relationships and interactions between individuals in communities as well as power relationships; past and present connected in stories; future desires and aspirations; and, finally, the intertwining of who we are with where we come from.

1.7 Employer branding and storytelling

Since the reflexion of (Boje, 1991) on the organization storytelling, a multitude of publications have been published on the stories that individuals tell within and about organizations (Mosberg, 2008), as well as the stories that individuals tell about getting a job with an organization (Berkelaar, Birdsell & Scacco, 2016). In addition, numerous studies have been conducted on online communication and on the social networks of organizations in order to develop their corporate image (Edmiston, 2016). According to (Crişan & Borţun, 2017), there is a close relationship between employer branding and strategic recruitment. (Wilden, Gudergan & Lings, 2010) conclude that the effectiveness of a brand signal to potential employees depends on consistency, clarity and credibility and related investments in the employer brand.

(Grünewälder, 2007) defines employer branding as the process of placing the image of a great place to work in the mind of the target group. An employer brand creates an image that makes the targeted candidate want to work for the employer organization because of the image of a well-managed space where workers learn and grow continuously. (Backhaus & Tikoo 2004,) define employer branding as the process of creating an identifiable and unique employer identity. Storytelling could be used as a means of increasing the employer brand by bringing more authenticity and legitimation into the communication of organizations targeting highly qualified workers.

2. Theoretical framework

2.1 Theory of social representations

According to (Buschini, Lorenzi-Cioldi, 2013) the theory of social representations, was developed by Serge Moscovici in 1961 and is based on the premise that people reason in several ways. Many scholars share this notion. In the sociology field, Émile Durkheim cited by (Buschini, Lorenzi-Cioldi, 2013) distinguishes individual and collective representations. According to this author, individual representations are unique cognitive states.

According to (Buschini, Lorenzi-Cioldi, 2013), Moscovici places social representations in a dynamic position between psychology and sociology. This view argues that representations are both social objects that change with human interaction and cognitive objects that have internal structure and coherence. The study of psychological functioning was based on the postulate that internal psychological states, conceived as individual cognitive activities, are both the product and the generator of behaviours, opinions and attitudes. From the 1960s, two distinct paths were taken to study the representative activities of individuals. The first, which dominated the Anglo-Saxon world, dealt with cognitive biases in perception and judgment. Moscovici introduced another approach that considers social representations as means of communication that articulate social and psychological aspects, thus rejecting the notion that biases affect human thoughts. Studying social representations is an effective way to observe and understand how human groups interpret and construct, both semantically and symbolically, their reality and to understand how the representation of social environment influences their behaviours and interactions. These teachings of the theory of social representations (Moscovici, 1961) are now well established. In forty years, social representations have established themselves as an important field of investigation in social psychology.

The common sense needs a base on which to assemble elements. This base is constituted by

individuals, semantic and symbolic content. The links and coherence of these elements are established through communication that plays an essential role in common sense, representing a real vehicle for social representations, by ensuring their development and transmission.

The approach based on discursive or iconic analysis: According (Buschini, Lorenzi-Cioldi, 2013) social representations can be studied through language by examining how they are formed in discourse. This approach of social representations is predominant in United Kingdom and focuses mainly on language as construction and social interaction. It can be developed using definitional (Lahlou 1998), narrative (Jovchelovitch, 2002; Laszlo, 2002), dialogical (Markova, 2003), rhetorical (Billig, 1993), metaphorical (Lakoff & Johnson, 1980), discourse analysis (Parker & Burman, 1993).

This approach considers that language is the main or only means of accessing to social thinking. It is difficult to obtain precise results with this approach because it is based on the interpretation of qualitative materials and is often illustrated by extracts from interviews. Interviews are thus used to establish conclusions, which are considered empirical facts that contribute to the discursive construction of representations and social reality.

2.2 Theory of trust

Before addressing the role of trust in predicting the adoption of a behavior, we first propose to identify the main dimensions of the concept. The notion is polysemic, (Boughanbouz, 2015) points out that despite the many definitions of trust, there is a consensus among the authors on the following dimensions: Mutuality, Vulnerability, Opportunism, Expectations and Risks in Construction. According to the same author there are many definitions of trust, and it is possible to see the presence of these essential elements, most of the work in the psychological, sociological and recently managerial literature agree, that trust is the expectation that a partner does not engage in opportunistic behaviour, even in the face of opportunities and incentives to opportunism. The abstract and multidimensional character of this concept appears with the observation of the many scientific disciplines that have approached it: sociology, psychology, economics, organizational behaviour.

Knowledge plays a structuring role in the formation of trust insofar as it reduces perceived uncertainty. This knowledge materializes in symbolic and material elements of the social environment (organizations, standards, values, institutions, etc.). The relationship with other social actors is built on the same cognitive basis and structures mutual trust. Sharing the same

culture or local context tends to facilitate the establishment of a social bond and a relationship of trust between actors (Gléonnec, 2004) cited by (Abderrahman A., 2018).

In the same context, communication can be considered as a means of transmitting symbolic and material elements that allow a better knowledge of its environment. (Gléonnec, 2004) cited by (Abderrahman A., 2018) uses the term "appropriation" to represent this knowledge of the social environment.

This appropriation, explains the author, acts in return in the form of more or less voluntary acts of communication for the social network: «the chain of appropriations and actions individuals within this network, through communication, thus contributes to organizational and social change, while strengthening the social bond» (Gléonnec, 2001) cited by (Abderrahman A., 2018). Trust is naturally formed in the context of this communicational process, by supporting exchanges between individuals or, when established in social structures, by regulating these exchanges. The present trust is the key to the future trust in the social structure based on the information gathered through the various forms of communication within the social network.

3. Conceptual Model by the authors

The proposal of this conceptual model is first the result of the observation of a lack of scientific literature that has not produced conceptual models highlighting the links between: diaspora, attractiveness of a territory/ organization and the brand through the practise of storytelling as an important tool to shape the brand image. It is also important to notice that several scientific works have emphasized the importance of the skilled diaspora role in the development of their countries of origin through knowledge transfer.

The qualified diaspora represents for the country of origin a reservoir of skills and a lever for the development of the motheland. The morrocan qualified diaspora play an important role in promoting the image of Morocco in many areas. It is therefore necessary to give importance to the practise of storytelling, considered as a branding tool at the level of networks of the skilled diaspora because of its ability to influence target perceptions, either attract them to work permanently in Morocco or mobilize them for punctual collaborations form.

Figure: Conceptual Model realized by (MATOUG & BOURIQUI, 2024)

Source: The authors of this paper

The proposal of this new conceptual model represents an innovative contribution in the sense that the mobilization and attraction of the qualified diaspora must be inspired by the discipline of marketing and more particularly branding through its tool storytelling that is an interesting way to attract and mobilize the targeted audience because of its ability to generate trust.

The proposal of this new conceptual model is the result of readings of several reports of international organizations and scientific papers that argue that the qualified diaspora has a role in the development of the country of origin. Storytelling by its performative character influences the perceptions and actions of the targeted audience and could be a promising perspective for our research context.

Conclusion

The subject of the attraction and mobilization of qualified diaspora represents a strategic challenge for the Moroccan State and an opportunity to take advantage of the expertise and

experience accumulated in the destination countries to bring added value. The skilled diaspora is the subject of a merciless international competition between different territories and organizations, on various scales as a result of globalization. New Public Management as a new paradigm consequence of globalization and neoliberalism described the public sector as inferior compared to the private sector. To this end, improving the quality of service provision and the relational approach has an effect on user satisfaction. This evolution in public managerial thinking has encouraged the emergence and transposition of several concepts from the marketing of private organizations to public organizations responsible for the management of a given geographical perimeter or sector.

The concepts of place brand/ organization brand employer are among these concepts, they have been widely studied by several authors who have made the link with attractiveness. The concept of storytelling as a brand tool has close connections with the notion of image, perception and representation having an effect on the behaviour of the target audience.

At the academic level, by proposing this new conceptual model, the integration of the concept of representation can bring an added value for the theoretical framework of branding described as insufficient according to several authors of scientific articles. The perspective presented by the social and human sciences and more particularly, social psychology could offer a window of perspectives to deepen reflection on the subject of branding and its relationship with the attraction and mobilization of skilled workers from the moroccan diaspora. At the managerial level, this new conceptual model could be an added value for organizations aiming to attract and mobilize the moroccan qualified diaspora. The adoption of the branding and the storytelling as a tool in the process of mobilizing and attracting skilled workers could be a promising perspective for these organizations wishing to benefit from the knowledge and know-how accumulated by these qualified diaspora in host countries. For the limitations of our research, this paper does not claim to have an exhaustive coverage of the existing scientific literature, it is based mainly on secondary data from scientific papers, theses, documents and official reports. Our experience in the field of migration was our first motivation and asset to develop a conceptual model to enrich the reflection and scientific literature. Our conceptual model will be the subject of a qualitative study to feed it and adjust it if the observation is made after the interpretation of the data that will be collected and analyzed from our targeted audience. We consider finally that this paper offer an innovative perspective of the mobilization and/or the attraction of moroccan qualified diaspora.

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